

Studies on the Effect of Some Ionic and Non ionic Surfactants on the Polarographic Maxima of Co(II)

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IN continuation to our previous publication¹ on the effect of some-ionic and non-ionic surfactants on the polarographic maxima of Cadmium-iodide complex, we now report our results of the studies on the effect of some ionic and non-ionic surfactants on polarographic maxima of Co(II).

Experimental

The experiments were carried out in a similar manner as described in the previous paper¹. However, a different capillary being used the d. m. e. had the following characteristics

$h_{\text{corr.}}$	= 61.20 cm.
m	= 1.92 mg/sec.
t	= 3.80 sec. (in 0.1M KCl, open circuit)
$m^{2/3} \cdot t^{1/6}$	= 1.932 mg ^{2/3} · sec ^{-1/6} .
Conc. of depolarizer	= $2 \times 10^{-3} M$
Conc. of supporting electrolyte (KCl)	= 0.1M

Results and Discussion

The polarographic characteristic properties of the surfactants, viz., Maximum suppression point² (MSP), Specific suppression coefficient³ (SSC) and Critical micelle concentration² (CMC) were defined and computed as reported in our previous publication¹. The values of these properties for cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactants have been tabulated in Table 1.

The maximum of Co(II) appears at -1.40 V (vs. S.C.E.) and hence it is of negative polarity. On comparing the characteristic properties especially MSP values for cationic and anionic surfactants from Table 1, it is found that the amount of the surfactant required to suppress the maxima of similar sign is greater than for those possessing dissimilar charges. This characterisation of the surfactants gives further support to the adsorption theory. Therefore, larger concentration of the anionic surfactant for negative maxima will be needed than for the cationic one, since the adsorption characteristics are to be prevented by the similarity of charges.

On considering LPB, TDPB and CPB in which chain length increases (C_{12} - C_{16}) while polar head size remains the same, it is found that the suppressive power of the surfactant increases with the increase in the chain length. Whereas in the case of CPB and CTAB in which the chain length is the same but different polar head size, it is found that the suppressive power increases with the increase of polar head size. The same is true with LPC; and CPC and CPB and CDBAC. Thus, it is evident that both chain length and polar head size determine the efficacy of a cationic surfactant in the suppression of negative maxima. These results are in conformity with those of Rusznak et al⁴.

The suppressive powers of the cationic surfactants are in the following order

The values of MSP, SSC and CMC for Manoxol-IB and Manoxol-OT reveal that the latter is more effective than the former in suppressing the maxima. This may be explained on the lines similar to those given in our previous paper¹.

TABLE 1

Surfactants	MSP	SSC	CMC
<i>Cationic</i>			
Lauryl pyridinium chloride	$27.50 \times 10^{-8} \%$	$10.85 \times 10^{-8} \%$	$0.76 \times 10^{-3} \%$
Lauryl pyridinium bromide	$21.25 \times 10^{-8} \%$	$10.00 \times 10^{-8} \%$	$1.00 \times 10^{-3} \%$
Tetradecyl pyridinium bromide	$4.00 \times 10^{-8} \%$	$1.25 \times 10^{-8} \%$	$0.50 \times 10^{-3} \%$
Cetyl pyridinium bromide	$3.98 \times 10^{-4} M$	$1.08 \times 10^{-4} M$	$1.00 \times 10^{-4} M$
Cetyl pyridinium chloride	$1.05 \times 10^{-3} \%$	$0.60 \times 10^{-3} \%$	$0.38 \times 10^{-3} \%$
Cetyl dimethyl benzyl amm. chloride	$2.00 \times 10^{-4} \%$	$0.20 \times 10^{-4} \%$	$0.10 \times 10^{-4} \%$
Cetyl trimethyl amm. bromide	$0.17 \times 10^{-4} M$	$0.01 \times 10^{-4} M$	$0.04 \times 10^{-4} M$
<i>Anionic</i>			
Manoxol-IB	$30.0 \times 10^{-3} M$	$14.50 \times 10^{-3} M$	$5.75 \times 10^{-3} M$
Manoxol-OT	$4.0 \times 10^{-4} M$	$1.40 \times 10^{-4} M$	$2.09 \times 10^{-4} M$
Tergitol-7	$10.0 \times 10^{-4} M$	$4.50 \times 10^{-4} M$	$2.50 \times 10^{-4} M$
Sodium lauryl sulphate	$25.0 \times 10^{-4} M$	$8.00 \times 10^{-4} M$	$2.89 \times 10^{-4} M$
Dodecyl benzene sulphonate	$40.0 \times 10^{-8} \%$	$10.84 \times 10^{-8} \%$	$6.61 \times 10^{-3} \%$
XL-Anionic	$8.0 \times 10^{-8} \%$	$2.50 \times 10^{-8} \%$	$1.82 \times 10^{-3} \%$
Methyl red	$20.0 \times 10^{-4} \%$	$4.80 \times 10^{-4} \%$	$3.98 \times 10^{-4} \%$
<i>Non-ionic</i>			
2-Ethoxy ethanol	3.80%	1.60%	1.096%
Ethyl diogol	0.30%	0.016%	0.022%
Triton X-100	$16.00 \times 10^{-4} \%$	$3.02 \times 10^{-4} \%$	$2.37 \times 10^{-4} \%$
Decon-90	$80.00 \times 10^{-4} \%$	$8.00 \times 10^{-4} \%$	$4.00 \times 10^{-4} \%$
Amido Black	$10.00 \times 10^{-4} M$	$4.00 \times 10^{-4} M$	$0.525 \times 10^{-4} M$

The suppressive powers of the anionic surfactants are in the following order :

Manoxol-OT > Tergitol-7 > Sodium lauryl sulphate > Manoxol-IB and Methyl red > XL-anionic > Dodecyl benzene sulphonate.

The suppressive powers of 2-ethoxy ethanol and ethyl dagol, are least among the non-ionic surfactants used. This is due to their low molecular weights. The efficacies of these neutral surfactants are in the following order :

Triton X-100 > Decon-90 > Amido black > Ethyldiagol > 2-ethoxyethanol.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Sulphadimethoxin Salicylaldehyde through its Copper Chelate

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SULPHONAMIDES are drugs of established therapeutic value. Butler and Ingle¹ have condensed sulphonamides with salicylaldehyde and have isolated various sulphonamide Salicylaldehydes. Tsukamoto and Yuhi^{2,3} have condensed sulphadiazine, Sulphamerazine and Sulphamethazine with 5 Bromo salicylaldehyde and 3, 5 dibromo salicylaldehyde. He also studied antibacterial activity of these bromo salicylaldehydes and found them to be active against mycobacterium tuberculosis. The complexes of Sulphadiazines salicylaldehydes have been studied with copper, nickel and cobalt by Jain and Chaturvedi⁴⁻⁶ and found 2 : 1 complexation.

Cupric ions react with SUDMSA forming a green coloured complex soluble in 50% ethanol. Based on this colour reaction a sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method has been developed for SUDMSA by which SUDMSA can be determined upto 50 μ g.

Experimental

All chemicals employed were of Analar grade. Sulphadimethoxin salicylaldehyde (SUDMSA) was prepared as described earlier⁷.

Absorbance measurements were made on a Beckmann model DV spectrophotometer and pH of the solution were checked using a pH meter (Beckmann model H-2). The pH of the solutions were adjusted by using different buffer solutions.

To prepare $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ solution, 41.4 mg. of SUDMSA was dissolved in 1 lit. of ethanol. The stock solution of copper was prepared using Analar grade copper acetate.

Results and Discussion

Sulphadimethoxin salicylaldehyde is light yellow in colour. The absorption spectra of SUDMSA shows three absorption bands at 222 nm, 241 nm and 278 nm. The complex is deep green in colour with an absorption maximum at 380 nm. at pH 6.5 which remains unaltered irrespective of the molar ratio of the components of the solution. This indicates the presence of only one complex in the solution under the conditions of study. The absorption by Copper acetate at λ_{max} of the complex is very low. The absorbance vs. pH plot shows that the absorption of the complex remains constant between pH 6-8. Thus a pH around 6.5 was kept for spectrophotometric study. The mole ratio plot shows that half moles of copper are sufficient for full colour development thus indicating that the metal and ligand are present in 1 : 2 ratio in the complex.

The system adheres to Beer's law.

Procedure : Take a suitable aliquot of SUDMSA solution in a 10 ml. volumetric flask, add sufficient excess of copper solution, 2 ml. Buffer solution followed by alcohol and water, so that final solution contains 50% (V/V) alcohol ; measure the absorbance at nm.

In this way it was possible to determine SUDMSA upto 50 μ g. quantities.

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